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Executive Summary

Introduction to the pilot specification notes

This report contains the pilot specification notes for the EURITO project. The purpose of the specification notes is to outline key contextual, methodological and practical points that both capture work that has been carried out to date and lay out the path ahead (up to the end of the Exploration Phase of the project, which is scheduled to conclude in February 2019).

Pilot selection

The pilot topics were selected at the conclusion of the project's Scoping Phase. The Scoping Phase included a range of exploratory efforts including stakeholder engagement, a literature review and the development of a data auditing framework.

Two-wave approach to pilot development

Following the selection of the pilot topics, a two-pronged approach was adopted by the consortium whereby four of the eight pilots would be more fully developed ahead of the September 2018 Knowledge Stakeholder Workshop (KSW), while the remaining four would be further developed following the KSW. The more developed projects fall into 'Wave 1' and the less developed into 'Wave 2'. The pilot specification notes are all structured within a similar framework, however the Wave 1 pilots are more detailed and include preliminary findings.

Wave 1 pilots:

- Pilot 1: Emerging tech ecosystems (AI)
- Pilot 2: Nowcasting business R&D
- Pilot 3: Technological change indicators
- Pilot 4: Standards as innovation diffusion indicators

Wave 2 pilots:

- Pilot 5: Evidence base for mission-oriented R&I
- Pilot 6: Advanced R&I funding analytics
- Pilot 7: Inclusive innovation
- Pilot 8: Linkages and knowledge exchange indicators (healthtech)

Next steps

All pilots will be further developed and refined ahead of the conclusion of the project's Exploration Phase in February 2019. At that point in the project, decisions will be taken around which pilots to scale up (e.g., expanding geographic or sectoral coverage) and/or how different, complementary components of the pilot portfolio can be combined and scaled.

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Pilot 1: Emerging Tech Ecosystems (AI)

Summary

- This pilot will develop indicators about emerging technologies and the status of 'emerging technology ecosystems' based on the analysis of open and web data. It will also explore options for identifying emerging technologies in a data-driven way. It is currently being developed through a case study of the AI R&D ecosystem in the EU.

Background/context

- There is strong policy interest in identifying and measuring emerging technologies with high growth potential, widespread applicability for many industries, first-mover advantage and potential side-effects, for example in terms of safety or impacts on employment. Some examples of such technologies include Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain or the Internet of Things. Better evidence about their development and diffusion can help R&I policymakers assess their country's or region's comparative advantage and identify gaps in the support ecosystem, leading to better interventions. Detailed information about key actors involved in the development of these technologies can inform stakeholder engagement and targeting during policy design and implementation, and help identify potential participants in the delivery of R&I missions where emerging technologies are often hoped to play an important role.
- Emerging technologies are by definition difficult to analyse using existing taxonomies and nomenclatures: their components and terminology are fluid, and they often appear in the intersection of academic disciplines, technology areas and sectors. This means that it is generally not possible to query official data sources and surveys to measure activity in emerging technologies.
- In addition to this, data sources which are less timely due to delays in data collection or publication (as is the case with patents and peer-reviewed publications) will not be suitable for generating the type of real-time data that R&I policymakers need in order to monitor, support and steer the development of emerging technologies.
- Emerging technologies evolve in complex ecosystems that involve multiple actors such as technology developers, research scientists, investors, skills suppliers, adopting organisations, regulators and funders. In order to understand the prospects for successful development of an emerging technology it is important to have access to information about these actors taking part in its development ecosystem.
- In this pilot, we use new data sources and analytical methods to map the development of Artificial Intelligence, a strategically important technology where there are concerns that the EU is losing ground against other countries.
- Stakeholder engagement summary
 - The analysis undertaken as part of this pilot provides timely and relevant evidence about the state of the AI emerging tech ecosystem. R&I policymakers might however be interested in more exploratory applications to discover new technologies of interest.
 - The pilot currently assumes that the vocabulary used to describe a technology is stable across corpora (data sources with different types of information and over time). It is also missing information in non-English languages.

- The pilot currently lacks information about the adoption of emerging technology in business.
- Bearing in mind all of the above, there is substantial interest in the pilot and its potential policy applications. The team has already been involved in conversations with the AI strategy team at DG RTD about how to continue developing the pilot to create an evidence base informing EU policy for this important technology.

Relevance to RITO criteria

- Relevant: Policymakers need detailed and timely information about emerging technologies to support and regulate them, and evaluate the impact of their interventions. The pilot provides this information.
- Inclusive: The pilot considers under-the-radar AI activities such as open source development and informal meetups. It also explores ways to measure the diffusion of AI in non-technology sectors.
- Trusted: The pilot includes traditional and new data sources. Findings will be validated with industry and policy experts, and triangulated with existing data.
- Open: The pilot uses primarily open data and its findings will be transparent and reproducible. The pilot already has resulted in a working paper using one of its experimental data sources (the arXiv pre-prints dataset) and an open source software repository with the code used in that analysis.

Research/policy questions

- What are the levels of activity in AI R&D in the EU and its member states, and how does it compare with the situation in other countries such as the USA, Canada or China?
- What is the configuration of national AI R&D ecosystems in different member states and what is their link with performance?
- Do we detect any inequalities in the geographical and sectoral distribution of AI activity?
- What are the levels and determinants of AI diffusion in different industries and locations?
- What is the structure of collaboration networks in AI R&D?
- What is AI’s position in wider networks of scientific activity? What fields are connected to it and what fields are further apart? What are the national differences across networks? What are the opportunities for recombining AI with other fields to generate innovative applications?

Data sources and methods

Source	Status	Observations
Publications and pre-prints data	We have analysed computer science pre-prints data from arXiv.	We still need to incorporate other publication data
Research funding	We have analysed H2020	Exploring options to

	funding data	include data from national EU funders
Open source	We have analysed data from GitHub	
Entrepreneurial activity	We have analysed data from CrunchBase	Exploring options to include other business data less skewed towards technology companies and start-ups
Informal networking activity	We have analysed data from Meetup	
Skills	We have access to data from university websites	To be collected and incorporated into the analysis
Patents		To be collected and incorporated into the analysis

We are currently integrating all the data into a single database that we query with Clio, an innovation information retrieval system that uses keyword-based searches to identify relevant documents in a corpus. Clio expands the initial query using word-embeddings in order to identify synonyms, and filters the list of synonyms to remove low salience (TF-IDF) terms within the keyword list. The results of the query are then mapped and analysed. Our analysis of sectoral activity is based on a supervised machine learning model that we train on the CrunchBase data, using company sectors as labels and their textual descriptions as predictors. This model is then used to predict likely sectors for projects in other datasets. We are currently using simple indicators such as project counts and revealed comparative advantage indices.

Outputs and preliminary findings

- Our analysis suggests that the EU is losing ground against other territories such as China, Canada, Singapore, Korea and the USA. This is particularly visible in the publications and open source software development data.
- The UK is the main hotspot of AI activity in the EU, followed by Germany, France, the Netherlands, Italy and Spain. Our ecosystem comparison suggests different AI ecosystem configurations:
 - UK and Ireland are stronger in research activity but weaker in entrepreneurial activity
 - Mediterranean countries have high levels of open source activity
 - Eastern European countries have strong entrepreneurial activity
- AI activity is highly concentrated in specific regions inside member states. AI activity is more concentrated than the population and overall R&D activity. There is stronger

geographical concentration in metrics of activity related to the commercial sector (businesses and meetups) than in research and research funding.

- We detect differences in the sectoral coverage of different data sources (sources of funding) and in the AI specialisation profiles of different countries.
 - H2020 appears to be funding AI projects with applicability in unusual sectors such as Agriculture or biotechnology.

Limitations

- There are some gaps in the data to be addressed in due course.
- Doubts about the representativity of some of the data (eg low Chinese presence in GitHub).
- Classification error in the model used to estimate sector distributions from the CrunchBase data (CrunchBase company descriptions tend to be short, there are some language overlaps between data sources / sectors that create challenges - for example, Meetup groups often use terminology related to events not because they are focused in AI applications to the events sector but because they are organizing events.).
- The indicators we have produced so far are quite simple (counts of activity and funding aggregates and revealed comparative advantage indices). Our maps of ecosystems are based on co-location rather than connectivity.

Validation and ongoing stakeholder engagement

- We will triangulate all our measures with Eurostat measures of industrial activity in relevant sectors; we will triangulate research activity metrics with traditional publications and official research activity measures.
- We are in conversations with DG RTD and European Research Council about their potential use of our data.

Considerations for scaling up

Complementarities with other pilots

- There are strong complementarities between this pilot and the pilot on structural technological change being run by DTU
- Overlaps in data sources between this pilot and the nowcasting / Structural technology change pilots.
- Emerging technology maps could be relevant for mission-oriented pilot.
- Analysis of geographical and sectoral inequality relevant for inclusive pilot.

Scaling up

- We would like to incorporate member state research funders
- We would like to measure diffusion of AI methods in business going beyond CrunchBase data which could be skewed towards digital technology applications.

Tools

- License PATSTAT data for the patent analysis?

Relevant conferences or events

- We have been invited to present our analysis of arXiv data at SPRU, Oxford University (Saïd Business School) and the Santa Fe Institute.
- [Add other potential conferences]

References

Bresnahan, T. F., & Trajtenberg, M. (1995). General purpose technologies 'Engines of growth'? *Journal of Econometrics*, 65(1), 83–108.

Brundage, M. (2016). Modeling Progress in AI. In *AAAI Workshop: AI, Ethics, and Society*.

Cockburn, I. M., Henderson, R., & Stern, S. (2018). The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Innovation. National Bureau of Economic Research.

Goldfarb, A., & Trefler, D. (2018). AI and International Trade. National Bureau of Economic Research.

Klinger, J., Mateos-Garcia, J. C., & Stathoulopoulos, K. (2018). Deep Learning, Deep Change? Mapping the Development of the Artificial Intelligence General Purpose Technology (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. ID 3233463). Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network. Retrieved from <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3233463>

Malerba, F. (2002). Sectoral systems of innovation and production. *Research policy*, 31(2), 247-264.

Rotolo, D., Hicks, D., & Martin, B. R. (2015). What is an emerging technology? *Research Policy*, 44(10), 1827–1843.

Pilot 2: Nowcasting Business R&D

Summary

This pilot will nowcast and placecast R&D expenditure in the EU based on the Business R&D Scoreboard ([link](#)), a dataset with detailed historical information from the top 2500 industrial investors on R&D from the EU and abroad based on their annual reports going back to 2004. JRC has already undertaken some nowcasting of these data using patents as a predictor. We will expand on that analysis using additional data and more advanced machine learning algorithms.

Background/context

- Although public R&D drives the generation of knowledge and talent needed by innovative enterprises, it is only through business investment that the full impacts of R&D can be realised. Business R&D integrates and transforms available knowledge into commercially viable technologies and innovation such as new products, processes and services that enable higher productivity, competitiveness, and efficiency.
- Business R&D is a policy relevant, lagging and expensive to collect innovation indicator. This pilot will therefore attempt to develop a nowcasting approach to predicting this information using machine learning models trained on public data such as company financials, publications and patenting, participation in collaborative research, demand for STEM skills etc.
- Understanding the drivers of BERD has been a topic of research for many years. For example, findings from a 2006 synthesis of studies conducted in OECD countries found that business R&D intensity is positively associated with R&D tax incentives (regardless of specification and estimation techniques) as well as expenditures on R&D performed by universities.

Stakeholder engagement workshops have identified important questions and considerations for this pilot, as well as existing similar projects. The level of granularity at which the nowcasting will be conducted emerged as a key point from workshop discussions. Different approaches will need to be taken, depending on whether the models are aimed at predicting enterprise, OECD sector classification, country, or regional level R&D expenditure. This choice of aggregation will impact structural differences that the model may need to take into account, for example, sectoral composition of different countries, or the geographical breakdown of an organisation's R&D spending. The scale of the entities that for which predictions will be made will also have an effect on the nature and amount of data required. In some regions or sectors, R&D spending will be dominated by just a few large actors. Stakeholders also highlighted the need for multivariate indicators, however pointed out that this has had limited success in the literature.

Other R&D nowcasting projects brought to our attention included an attempt by the ERC to nowcast including employment data. In Spain, attempts have been made to nowcast R&D expenditure, with national account variables providing the most successful predictors. In these studies, R&D spending has also been shown to be a strong predictor of BERD. In addition to the aforementioned JRC project, Eurostat have an ongoing project to nowcast R&D, making use of their own closed-source data. Through their studies, they have identified gaps that might be filled by further studies, including the scope of countries and sectors included. These

projects provide a baseline of what has been attempted, that can be used to assess the added value of including new data sources and variables for the pilot.

Relevance to RITO criteria

- Relevant: Business R&D is a highly policy relevant metric.
- Inclusive: By including new innovation activities as predictors (e.g. open source software development, interaction with startups based on analysis of press releases etc.) we might be able to identify 'hidden' types of innovation investment that influence R&D activity.
- Trusted: We will consider models with different levels of interpretability, and cross-validate results to ensure robustness.
- Open: To the greatest extent possible, this pilot will aim to use data that are openly available.

Research/policy questions

This pilot addresses the need for more timely R&D expenditure data. Current indicators are issued annually, and for the previous year, inducing significant lag. Multiple research questions will be addressed in order to attempt to provide more timely indicators.

- In order to use the scoreboard data to nowcast R&D investment it is crucial to detect the organisational and geographical structure of companies, in order to correctly attribute R&D spending. For example, an automobile company may have its headquarters in Germany, but an R&D site in the UK. This is a necessity if nowcasting is done in combination with placecasting but is also of paramount importance to reliably forecast as R&D activity in a particular nation/region will be influenced by variables specific to that geography such as skills availability, tax incentives, and co-location of similar industries. Additionally, a company may have subsidiaries that perform R&D activities and these may also be in different countries to the headquarters.
- What national or sub-national indicators predict R&D investment/activities? Is there a relationship between BERD and factors such as skills demand, start-up locations, policies, tech meetups?
- What conditions facilitate R&D investment? Based on the criteria established by the previous question what regions have unfilled potential for R&D investment due to market misallocation or agglomerative factors?

Data sources and methods

We will use a labelled dataset (the EU Industrial R&D scoreboard) to train a machine learning model to generate predictions about R&D activity. This can be applied to companies in the existing dataset, to generate higher frequency expenditure values, or to other companies for which these data are not available, as well as their countries and sectors.

- Data sources
 - The Business R&D Scoreboard
 - Publication and pre-print data
 - Patents
 - Research funding

- Business website data
 - STEM recruitment
 - GitHub activity
 - National economic indicators and information about public funding for research, R&I policies etc.
 - Online job adverts to assess demand for skills
 - Debate about whether patents are an appropriate data source to use in a nowcasting model given their lag
 - Geocoding R&D labs at NUTS3 level
 - Links between universities, companies, and other agencies
 - Commuting patterns
 - Movement of graduates
 - ORBIS data
 - National policies/targets for BERD
- **Methods:**
 - Deduplicate company names via Wikipedia / GRID
 - Geocode companies for matching with national indicators
 - Develop a strategy to apportion business R&D expenditure to different countries based in e.g. geographical distribution of patenting activity etc.
 - Collect predictor dataset (including information for unlabelled observations)
 - Feature engineering, training of ML models and cross-validation also considering interpretability
 - Analyse error at different levels of aggregation (companies, countries, sectors, countries-sectors) and select the right level of reporting.
 - Analyse the improvement in model performance (e.g. change in R^2 if using OLS) brought by different inputs.
 - Report findings through interactive visualisations with suitable strategies for communicating uncertainty about estimates.

Outputs and preliminary findings

Preliminary studies have explored the R&D expenditure of the top five companies (by absolute R&D spending) in the automotive, pharmaceutical, media and software industries in the EU since 2006. The trends and stability of R&D intensity over time within these companies varies greatly between sector. The pharmaceutical organisations spend the highest percentage, with the widest distribution, whereas the automobile industry spends considerably less across time, with a much tighter distribution across companies.

Univariate correlations between GitHub, publication, and patent activity with R&D spending intensity for these companies showed the wide variety of patterns that can be exhibited between the variables we can measure and R&D spending. For those companies that have a presence on GitHub, activity (based on code commits) showed a general upward exponential trend. However, across the companies, both positive, negative and no correlations were seen when GitHub activity was compared with R&D spending. We also observed that many companies, including software companies, have no presence on the platform.

Publication data shows good historic coverage and a general growth over time in the number of publications from companies that engage in academic publishing. However, it is unclear whether the trends seen among the larger companies are representative of smaller actors. Additionally, there are multiple methods for measuring publication activity, and the appropriateness of these may vary across sector and actor size. Patents also have a long historic coverage, and all companies in the subset that were explored had engaged in patenting, though this may change for smaller organisations. In general, patent activity showed a positive correlation with R&D intensity, however within each of the four sectors, there was no observable trend. It is also clear that patent activity varies regionally.

Finally, locations of startup companies on Crunchbase and tech community Meetups were identified across Europe. These were predictably concentrated around capital cities of Western European nations. However, coverage in both datasets existed across most EU countries, suggesting that they may be useful for making predictions with variables at the national level.

Limitations

- BERD is inextricably linked to economic factors such that nowcasting BERD necessitates nowcasting the economy - a multi-trillion dollar question - therefore the accuracy of any nowcasting approach we develop would not be valid under changing economic conditions.
- Due to the aggregated nature of BERD (a few firms in a few sectors spend most of the money) then one large company behaving atypically within a year by temporally increasing/decreasing R&D spending by a large amount or being subject to a merger/acquisition will greatly affect global BERD.
- A limitation will be the extent to which we are able to geographically apportion R&D activities of a company which is a key research focus of this pilot.
- One concern around using data such as patents and publications is the lag between the release of these documents and when the related R&D effort actually occurred. This lag may have to be analysed before nowcasting models are developed, to understand its nature.
- Another limitation for tracking companies over time is that they may change their names or merge with other countries. Name changes make data matching more difficult and will require the use of fuzzy matching or a comprehensive dictionary. Mergers and buyouts may cause companies to disappear from some datasets, but they may remain in others due to the lag mentioned above. They may also cause discontinuities in R&D expenditure.
- Data coverage is non-uniform across countries and sectors. This may require individual models to be built, based on different datasets for each region or industrial sector.

Validation and ongoing stakeholder engagement

- In a first instance, we can connect bilaterally with statistical bodies that are currently involved in producing business R&D statistics (e.g. the UK's ONS, Eurostat). Given the importance of this indicator within the innovation landscape, it will be crucial to ensure the methodology and results are validated prior to any efforts to scale up.

Considerations for scaling up

- The work that has been carried out on this pilot to date has been at a relatively small scale, so there is much exploratory work to be carried out in terms of broadening its scope and coverage. Several of the geographic and industry-specific considerations that might affect this scaling process are described in the sections above, and will be examined in more depth moving forward.
- The team carrying out this pilot has the capacity to perform any scaling required, and should not require additional resources/support.

Relevant conferences or events

- We anticipate that there will be opportunities to share - perhaps through bespoke events - the results of this pilot with a community of statistical practitioners who are currently involved in the production of BERD statistics (organisations listed above). We will endeavour to find opportunities to share the work with wider audiences within the statistics and innovation communities.

References

Becker, B. (2015). Public R&D policies and private R&D investment: A survey of the empirical evidence. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 29(5), 917-942.

Doloreux, D., Shearmur, R., & Rodriguez, M. (2016). Determinants of R&D in knowledge-intensive business services firms. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 25(4), 391-405.

Gkotsis, P., Hernandez, H., & Vezzani, A. (2016). Estimating territorial business R&D expenditures using corporate R&D and patent data (No. JRC103127). Joint Research Centre (Seville site).

Guzman, J., & Stern, S. (2015). Nowcasting and placecasting entrepreneurial quality and performance (No. w20954). National Bureau of Economic Research.

Moat, H. S., Curme, C., Stanley, H. E., & Preis, T. (2014). Anticipating stock market movements with Google and Wikipedia. In *Nonlinear phenomena in complex systems: From nano to macro scale* (pp. 47-59). Springer, Dordrecht.

Pilot 3: Technological Change Indicators

Summary

- The proposed pilot focus is on R&I indicators able to capture technological change based on recombinant innovation and economic complexity approaches. We use worldwide bioenergy R&D as the application domain to allow for an in-depth interpretation of results with domain experts. For this purpose we have had exploratory discussions with the EU Joint Research Centre (JRC) focusing on Energy, The Nordic Institute for Studies in Innovation, Research and Education (NIFU), and are also considering involving JRC Innovation and Growth, who could be one of our stakeholder champions.

Background/context

- **Opportunity:** We currently lack R&I indicators capturing technological change. Unless a technology is pre-catalogued, it is invisible to current official instruments. This means that policymakers have a blind spot when it comes to the understanding of technological change that might affect the allocation of resources, the design of regulations and the evaluation of R&I progress.
- **Application domain:** The overall application domain we used in this pilot can be described as “Research and development of bioenergy solutions”. In this context, bioenergy can be understood as “renewable energy made available from materials derived from biological sources”. This form of energy is considered one of the key elements needed to diversify our energy production alternatives, among other things because some implementations allow producing energy with a negative carbon footprint. Despite the potential that bioenergy holds, the world is currently at a stage where we need to significantly increase the performance of current solutions, and simultaneously reduce the costs and time to market. Only in this way bioenergy technologies can have the strong environmental and economic impact that is required for large-scale implementations. We are proposing this application domain because of:
 - Its inherent potential for societal impact (market-pull).
 - Worldwide availability of quality data-sources both traditional and non-traditional.
 - Access to application domain experts that can help us to validate and interpret our results.
- **Flexibility of application domain:** We have designed the indicators for technological change in such a way that they can be transferred across domains with minimal need for modifications. The main challenge is that moving to other application domains might require some degree of customisation of the internal dictionaries of taxonomies. For this reason, we are already evaluating cross-domain dictionaries and taxonomies that can be obtained from platforms such as DBpedia and WikiData.
- **Assessment of 'periphery to core of R&I policy' capacity of proposed pilot:** R&I indicators for technological emergence have not been “institutionalised” yet. Furthermore, most previous attempts are not based on combinatorial innovation metrics. Taking such “peripheric” indicators into the core can be facilitated by the champions that we have considered for this pilot.

- **Stakeholder engagement summary**

- We have engaged as stakeholders the EU Joint Research Centre (JRC) (Energy and transport area), The Nordic Institute for Studies in Innovation, Research and Education (NIFU), the Research Policy journal through his editor John Walsh and assistant professor Stanko Skec from the University of Zagreb whom we worked with on the fundamentals of technological change indicators.
- The response we have obtained so far from the interactions with the stakeholders indicates that 1) the approach we are taking is not something they have seen applied in this context 2) they believe the database coverage is appropriate and sufficiently representative of the application domain and 3) the results align with their understanding of the overall patterns of technological change in the sector.
- Feedback highlights from the knowledge stakeholder workshop (KSW) include a) the possibility of exploring different technological change patterns per country in order to analyse stages of development, and/or technological specialisation at the regional or organizational levels , b) we should evaluate means to go from our originally descriptive to a potentially predictive analysis, taking advantage of the observed trends, and c) analyse how technological changes might exhibit different patterns depending on the data source used. For example, how does it compare the technological change pattern found within the corpus of patents with the patterns of scientific publications and/or grants.

Relevance to RITO criteria

- **Relevant:** the pilot tackles an issue that has been already mentioned as something that is necessary to improve in the context of R&D indicators, and it is also of high societal relevance.
- **Inclusive:** We are setting a worldwide scope, including developing and developed countries in the data-pool. As our emphasis is also in network structure, not scale, we believe this helps to highlight unique/innovative solutions that emerge from countries that produce a relatively small volume of outputs. Furthermore, we combine industrial and academic outputs and the data inputs can be expanded to include data related to SMEs and any other data-source available.
- **Timely:** Our addition of data sources other than patents and publications allow us to identify signals that might be expressed earlier on in other sources. Furthermore, focusing not just on keywords, but on the combination of technological building blocks allows earlier identification of unique technological changes.
- **Trusted:** Combining traditional/curated data sources with non-traditional sources allows us to leverage the trust put in official sources whilst also enjoying the complementary advantages of alternative sources.
- **Open:** All our proposed methods and data for this proposed pilot are already publicly available (at least in some form). We will also document the analytical steps taken so that they are reproducible.

Research/policy questions

- What is the year-to-year rate of technological change? For example, are we in a relatively stable and incremental period or in a period where the rates of change seem to point to radical departures from our previous technological trajectories?
- Which technologies are the biggest contributors to the overall pattern of technological change measured in a given period?
- How unique/new is a given technology?

Data sources and methods

Source	Status	Observations
Publications and pre-prints data	We have analysed worldwide bioenergy and biofuel publications from Web of Science.	Web of Science requires a subscription (that most universities have) and allows data mining for research purposes. However for other uses or situations where a license is not available we can substitute Web of Science with open access publication repositories.
Research funding	We have analysed H2020 funding data	Exploring options to include data from other EU funding organisations
Data generated by previous EU projects working on bioenergy and worldwide bioenergy agencies	We have included data extracted from Bioenergy2020+, ETIP Bioenergy, Biofuel Digest and Genscape databases. These data sources exist as openly accessible websites that contain repositories with bioenergy projects, feedstocks and processing technologies.	The heterogeneous set of data-sources used in this category might need to be streamlined before scaling up
Patents	We have analysed worldwide bioenergy and biofuel publications extracted from Derwent.	Derwent requires a subscription (which some universities have) and allows data mining for research purposes. However for other uses or situations where a license is not available we can substitute Derwent with

		open patent publication databases (e.g. patent lens).
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Data infrastructure and analytics: The first step requires normalising the data, which was done through an ETL process that allows us to load semi-structured data into a graph database. Within the graph database, we applied network analysis techniques to quantify structural network changes over time focusing on combinatorial innovation processes. The overall method can be summarised by three main steps, a) creating a document-terms matrix for each year, b) a term-term matrix per year, and finally c) a matrix summarising year-to-year changes capturing the evolution of the network of terms (as seen in the figure below)

Other methods we applied include

- Semantic modelling of the application domain using pre-existent taxonomies and ontologies
- Development of graph models able to capture the network structure of a technological space
- Design of algorithms to measure structural changes in network over time
- Development and testing of visualisations to communicate structural changes of networks over time in an easily “digestible” format

Outputs and preliminary findings

- We have experimented with a range of network and matrix based approaches to visualise changes in network structures. In addition to these approaches we have also transferred the results into more conventional representations showing rate of technological change over time (which we connected to the matrix or network representations to allow for context exploration).
- Additional applications of these type of outputs include support to the evaluation of mission-oriented R&I impact as we can use some of the elements of these approach to identify the degree of technological change that occurred after an intervention or funding action.

Limitations

- Developed indicator does not capture impact, performance, cost, etc. Focus is on early stage R&D and on overall technological change
- The interpretation of terms co-occurrence is valid only on aggregate. This means that the observation of a change in a pair of terms such as “Algae - Biodiesel” should not be interpreted in isolation. To correctly interpret changes in the usages of terms or term pairs is necessary to consider how all other terms and/or term pairs change and the overall volume of documents. At the aggregate level, the indicator for technological change that we developed takes into consideration both the volume of documents and entire set of changes a whole.
- Relation between volume of document records and opportunity to explore space of combinatorial possibilities requires additional work to avoid misinterpretations

Validation and ongoing stakeholder engagement

- We will continue our engagement with The Nordic Institute for Studies in Innovation, Research and Education (NIFU) and the rest of the stakeholders.
- In order to validate the empirical results of our method we will involve bioenergy and biofuel researchers at DTU that can compare the patterns that we found against their own experience and the literature base.
- Our plan is that the rest of the activities aimed at validation and ongoing stakeholder engagement will be primarily carried on through bilateral discussions that will allow us to go into the high-level of detail needed at this stage of the work.

Considerations for scaling up

Complementarities with other pilots

- This pilot is highly complementary with the efforts carried out in pilot #1, emerging technology ecosystems in AI, as it allows bridging the micro-level patterns identified in pilot 1 against the macro-level technological changes identified in this pilot.
- There is an interesting opportunity to combine the usage of standards promoted in pilot “Pilot 4 Standards as indicators for the diffusion of innovation”. This can be done by integrating a corpus of standards and/or regulations as an additional datasource within the same methodology and running the same analyses.

Scaling up

- The main challenge to scaling up relates to the creation of standard cross-domain taxonomies or dictionaries. The method has been tested with different combinations of dictionaries and is robust to changes but all the tests have been performed within the context of bioenergy R&D. If we decide to move elements of this pilot to the scaled-up cases the first task will be to build large cross-domain dictionaries extracting entities from sources such as DBpedia and WikiData.

Tools

- The main tools used in this pilot are a Graph Database running on Neo4j, Python and Jupyter Notebooks (where we have documented each step of the process).

Relevant conferences or events

- Participation in the event “RISIS SMS Linked Data for Science and Innovation Studies: Using the SMS platform for enriching your research data” (June 11th - 12th 2018)
- Guest presentation at Data Natives Copenhagen (Sept, 4th 2018) and Berlin (Nov 25th 2018) where part of the current progress made in pilot 3 is presented
- Guest presentation of our pilot 3 project at the concluding conference of “Research Output & Impact Analyzed and Visualized” (Oct 3rd, 2018)

References

Beykikhoshk, A., Arandjelović, O., Phung, D., & Venkatesh, S. (2018). Discovering topic structures of a temporally evolving document corpus. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 55(3), 599-632.

Frenken, K., Izquierdo, L. R., & Zeppini, P. (2012). Branching innovation, recombinant innovation, and endogenous technological transitions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 4, 25-35.

Joung, J., & Kim, K. (2017). Monitoring emerging technologies for technology planning using technical keyword based analysis from patent data. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 114, 281-292.J

Korotayev, A., Zinkina, J., & Bogevolnov, J. (2011). Kondratieff waves in global invention activity (1900–2008). *Technological forecasting and social change*, 78(7), 1280-1284.

Lee, W. S., Han, E. J., & Sohn, S. Y. (2015). Predicting the pattern of technology convergence using big-data technology on large-scale triadic patents. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 100, 317-329.

Schoenmakers, W., & Duysters, G. (2010). The technological origins of radical inventions. *Research Policy*, 39(8), 1051-1059.

Kim, G., & Bae, J. (2017). A novel approach to forecast promising technology through patent analysis. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 117, 228-237.

Youn, H., Strumsky, D., Bettencourt, L. M., & Lobo, J. (2015). Invention as a combinatorial process: evidence from US patents. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, 12(106), 20150272.

Pilot 4: Standards as Innovation Diffusion Indicators

Summary

The pilot on standards has the objective to use certifications of selected international management standards released by the Industrial Organization for Standardization (ISO) as indicators for the diffusion of innovation. Descriptive statistics of time series and distributions among sectors are displayed and regional heatmaps of indicators are constructed as certifications per number of companies in the EU28. The data collected and provided by ISO have been successfully validated in the case of Germany with data disclosed at the homepages of almost 1.5 million German companies out of the around 3 million German companies.

Background/context

The majority of research and innovation indicators focus on the creation of inventions and innovations. Only a few output and even fewer indicators measure the diffusion of innovations. However, only the diffusion of innovation generates real economic impact. Standards contribute to the diffusion of innovation (Robertson & Gatignon 1986) and have therefore obviously this economic impact, e.g. on economic growth, trade, shares in value chains, but also profits (e.g. Wakke et al. 2016). The number of certifications of international management standards have mainly been used to explain international trade flows (Clougherty and Grajek 2008, 2014), but also the diffusion of environmental innovations (Lim and Prakash 2014). However, the certifications of different types of standards implemented in companies can be considered as important types of routines defined as regular and predictable firm patterns (Nelson and Winter 1982) and therefore as process innovations. At the macro level, standards are important technology infrastructure (Tassey 2000) and contribute to innovation-friendly framework conditions (Blind et al. 2017).

In this pilot, we explore how certifications of international management standards can be used to track process innovations to improve productivity and quality, but also addressing sustainability issues in the EU.

Stakeholder engagement summary

The OECD has realised the need to expand their definition of innovation and has – also based on the input provided by Fraunhofer – consequently included standardization in the 4th edition of the Oslo Manual (OECD 2018). In detail, it claims the adoption of Total Quality Management (TQM), part of the ISO 9000 family of standards is another organisational capability that is closely related to innovation. Furthermore, standards have been included in the sources of ideas and information for innovation and the elements of the external environment for business innovation. Compliance with standards is also within the innovation objectives as well as the innovation drivers. In addition the active contribution to standards is also perceived as innovation objective. Overall, standards and standardisation play an important coordination role in many markets and can influence the characteristics of product and business process innovations.

In parallel, the European Commission includes standards as an output indicator in the Interim Evaluation of Horizon 2020. In addition, there is a strong interest in DG GROW in the growth and trade related impacts of standards and in DG CONNECT in the important role of standards for the interoperability of ICT.

Finally, the team is in contact with national, like in Germany DIN, European, like CEN, and international standardisation bodies, like ISO, to discuss and promote standards as innovation indicators.

Relevance to RITO criteria

- **Relevant:** Policymakers need detailed and timely information about the diffusion of standards as indicators both of the self-regulatory infrastructure and of process innovations in order to support them and evaluate the impact of regulatory interventions. The pilot provides this information for quality, environmental, IT security and energy efficiency management.
- **Inclusive:** International standards released by ISO are developed in a consensus process involving all relevant stakeholders; in addition ISO covers emerging topics, like blockchain, but also includes societal or environmental aspects.
- **Timely:** The data of ISO standards are immediately updated, the certification data have a time lag of one year.
- **Trusted:** The data are provided by ISO, a UN organisation. In addition, standardisation processes follow a strict consensual process. Findings are validated and triangulated with data collected from companies' homepages.
- **Open:** The pilot uses in general open data and its findings will be transparent and reproducible.

Research/policy questions

The pilot addresses the question of whether standards can be used as an indicator for the diffusion of innovation. Following the positive outcome of a feasibility test, it is possible to address the following questions:

- What is the diffusion rate of (management) standards over time?
- What is the diffusion rate of (management) standards across countries?
- How do the indicators correlate with the indicators of the European Innovation Scoreboard?

Data sources and methods

- We used the metadata of around 20.000 ISO standards. This metadata can also be linked to scientific publications referenced in the standards and to patents to be declared essential for the implementation of the standards. However, we focus the pilot on the data about the certifications based on the most important ISO management standards, like the more than one million certifications based on the ISO 9001 standard on quality management and the more than 300,000 certifications related to ISO 14000, the environmental management standard.

- We analysed the data primarily in a descriptive way in order to show the usability of standards and related certifications as a diffusion indicator, but we will also produce heat maps by countries.
- The application domain is focused on the management standards released by ISO. Therefore, the application domain is very generic with the restriction that ISO standards do not consider electrotechnical topics in the narrower sense.

Outputs and preliminary findings

The number of ISO 9001 certifications related to quality management and 14001 certifications on environmental management are stagnating in most EU countries, whereas the certificates related to ISO 27001 on information security management and ISO 50001 on energy management are – starting from a much lower level – continuously increasing.

The machinery sector is taking around one third of the ISO 9001 and ISO 14001 and one quarter of the ISO 50001 certificates, whereas more than half of the ISO 27001 certificates can be found in companies active in the information technology.

Italy has the highest intensity of ISO 9001 certificates of around 4% followed by Germany measured as number of certifications divided by the number of companies. Surprisingly, Romania is leading the ranking of ISO 14001 again followed by Italy and the United Kingdom. Whereas the United Kingdom has the highest density in ISO 27001 certificates reflecting the strong IT sector, Germany is number one in the energy management certificates ISO 50001 probably reflecting the change in the energy system.

Whereas the intensities between ISO 9001 and ISO 14001 are highly correlated, the links to the rather new certificates ISO 27001 and ISO 50001 are rather weak. This underlines that the former two are more part of the institutional framework, whereas the latter represent the diffusion of process innovations.

Finally, the correlation analysis with the indicators of the European Innovation Scoreboard reveals rather low values of coefficients. Only ISO 27001 correlates positively with opportunity-driven entrepreneurship, whereas ISO 50001 correlates positively with R&D and non-R&D expenditure in the business sector, Enterprises providing ICT training, PCT patent applications, Design applications, Employment in knowledge-intensive activities and employment in fast-growing firms innovative sectors. The latter is also positively correlated with ISO 27001.

Using certifications of international management standards normalised by countries' number of companies is an innovation indicator for process innovation. It reflects on the one hand the recent integration of standards in the 4th edition of the OECD Oslo Manual. On the other hand, the indicator can be easily integrated as a further complementary indicator for process innovations in the set of indicators used for the calculation of the European Innovation Scoreboard. In addition, the indicator can also be constructed for the most important countries outside the European Union.

Limitations

- Data quality of certifications is continuously improved, in particular in some countries, which restricts the validity of some country-specific time series.
- Updates of certification schemes due to new editions of international management standards might create frictions in time series.
- The number of companies provided by Eurostat is not updated in all EU Member States to 2017, which challenges the harmonisation of the indicators.

Validation and ongoing stakeholder engagement

We triangulated the ISO data on certifications of the selected management data for Germany with insights from information extracted from firm websites using web scraping. Based on the total population of around 1.5 million firm websites in Germany, the aggregated number of certificates provided by ISO could be validated, i.e. the number of companies disclosing certifications is very similar to the numbers provided by ISO. In addition, information about the distribution of certifications over company size and regional location could be revealed.

Since standardisation is acknowledged as an innovation activity and standards as an output for research or market integration in the [interim evaluation of Horizon 2020](#) and standardisation has been integrated in the 4th edition of the Oslo Manual (OECD 2018), it can be expected that the pilot will contribute to the capacity of standardisation to be moved to the core of R&I policy. In addition to DG Research and Innovation, the currently running [Joint Initiative on Standardisation](#) endorsed by DG GROW is interested in the impacts of European standards in general, but also on innovation in particular. Here, Fraunhofer is directly involved in a - not yet published - feasibility study about impacts. In addition, standards are an important element for the integration of the [Single Market](#) in general and the Single Digital Market in particular. Further support can be expected by the European standardisation bodies [CEN](#) and [CENELEC](#), which have a strong focus on innovation and have recently published an [innovation plan](#) aiming to open their standardisation processes and standards to innovators and researchers. Knut Blind is Chairman of a Working Group Standardisation Innovation and Research STAIR, which is collecting data about standards as output of Horizon 2020. ISO created in 2013 the [ISO/TC 279 Innovation Management](#), which was closely linked to the OECD activities related to the 4th edition of the Oslo Manual. Consequently, support from ISO/TC 279, to which links have been established by Knut Blind during the drafting of the new edition of the Oslo Manual, can be expected. At the national level, the German Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy have integrated standardisation in their transfer programmes and it is expected that it will play an important role in the currently prepared new transfer strategy. Knut Blind is in close exchange with the ministry in preparing the new transfer strategy in order to assure that standardisation is adequately integrated.

Considerations for scaling up

Complementarities with other pilots

Standardisation activities in Artificial Intelligence and the Bioeconomy have been considered to be integrated in Pilot 1 on Emerging Tech Ecosystems being run by Nesta and Pilot 3 on structural technological change being performed by DTU. Standardisation could be also relevant for the mission-oriented pilot.

Scaling up

Since the pilot is based on international standards, it is already positioned at the European or even international level. However, the option of generating further insights from extracting information about companies' certifications related to international management standards from firm websites of other EU Member States in addition to Germany using web scraping has to be proved. It contribute to the validation of the web scraping approach performed in Germany

Tools

The feasibility of scaling up the web scraping in other EU Member States has to be checked and might require additional external resources, which currently cannot be specified.

Relevant conferences or events

- Waiting for proofs of an article "Standardization and Standards as Science and Innovation Indicators" forthcoming in: Springer Handbook of Science and Technology Indicators <https://www.springer.com/us/book/9783030025106>
- Waiting for reviewers' feedback on an article "Standardization in the Context of Evolutionary Economics" as conceptual basis for the pilot forthcoming in: Handbook of Research Methods and Applications in Industrial Dynamics and Evolutionary Economics edited by Edward Elgar
- Paper "The Influence of Standardization, Patenting and Publishing on Firm Performance" by Knut Blind, Fraunhofer FOKUS & TU Berlin & Stephan Lhuillery ICN Business School & BETA & Markus Simeth Copenhagen Business School has been presented at EPIP 2018 at September 6th 2018 in Berlin and will be developed further to be submitted to a scientific journal
- Paper "Paving the Path: Drivers of Standardization Participation at ISO" by Knut Blind, Fraunhofer FOKUS & TU Berlin & Max von Laer has been submitted to a Special Issue about standardisation of IEEE Transaction on Engineering Management
- Further papers can be presented at the annual conference of EURAS, the European Academy for Standardisation e.V., in June 2019 in Rome, 14th Annual Conference of the European Policy for Intellectual Property Association 2019, September 11-13 in Zurich, Switzerland, the 24th Science and Technology Indicator Conference 2019 in Rome and Atlanta Conference on Science and Innovation Policy, October 14-16, 2019, at the Georgia Institute of Technology.

References

Blind, K. (2018): Standardization and Standards as Science and Innovation Indicators, forthcoming in: Springer Handbook of Science and Technology Indicators.

Blind, K. (2019): Standardization in the Context of Evolutionary Economics, forthcoming in: Handbook of Research Methods and Applications in Industrial Dynamics and Evolutionary Economics

Blind, K.; Mangelsdorf, A.; Niebel, C.; Ramel, F. (2018): Standards in the global value chains of the European Single Market, in: Review of International Political Economy 2018, 25 (1), 28-48.

Blind, K.; Mangelsdorf, A.; Pohlisch, J. (2018): The effects of cooperation in accreditation on international trade: Empirical evidence on ISO 9000 certifications, in: International Journal of Production Economics. 2018, 198, 50-59

Blind, K.; Pohlisch, J.; Zi, A. (2018): Publishing, Patenting and Standardization: Motives and Barriers of Scientists, in: Research Policy, 47, 1185-1197.

Blind, K.; Petersen, S.; Riillo, C. (2017): The Impact of Standards and Regulation on Innovation in Uncertain Markets, in: Research Policy 46 (1), 249–264.

Clougherty, J.A. & M. Grajek (2008): The impact of ISO 9000 diffusion on trade and FDI. A new institutional analysis. J. Int. Bus. Stud. 39 (4), 613–633.

Clougherty, J.A. & M. Grajek (2014): International standards and international trade. Empirical evidence from ISO 9000 diffusion. Int. J. Ind. Organ. 36, 70–82.

European Commission (2017): Intervention logic of Horizon 2020 interim evaluation, https://ec.europa.eu/research/evaluations/pdf/archive/h2020_evaluations/intervention_logic_h2020_052016.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none

Levine D. I & M. W. Toffel (2010): Quality Management and Job Quality: How the ISO 9001 Standard for Quality Management Systems Affects Employees and Employers. Management Science 56(6):978-996.

Lim, S. & A. Prakash (2014): Voluntary Regulations and Innovation: The Case of ISO 14001. Public Administration Review, 74, 233–244.

Nelson R.R.; Winter S.G (1982): An evolutionary theory of economic change. Harvard Univ. Press. Cambridge, MA

OECD, ETF, EU, EBRD, SEECEL (2016): SME Policy Index: Western Balkans and Turkey 2016: Assessing the Implementation of the Small Business Act for Europe, OECD Publishing, Paris.

OECD/Eurostat (2018): Oslo Manual 2018: Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation, 4th Edition, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris/Eurostat, Luxembourg.

Robertson, T.S. & H. Gatignon (1986): Competitive effects on technology diffusion. Journal of Marketing 50, 1–12.

Tassey, G., (2000): Standardization in technology-based markets. Research Policy 29, 587–602.

Wakke, P.; Blind, K.; Ramel, F. (2016): The impact of participation within formal standardization on firm performance, Journal of Productivity Analysis, 45(3), 317-330.

Pilot 5: Evidence base for mission-oriented R&I

Summary

- EU policymakers are developing a new framework for R&I based on the idea of missions: big societal challenges that will be addressed by combining the knowledge from different disciplines in ambitious projects and programmes. This pilot will produce maps and metrics to inform the design and implementation of mission-oriented research and innovation in the EU.

Background/context

- Brief literature review
 - Mission-oriented policies can be defined as systemic public policies that draw on frontier knowledge to attain specific goals or “big science deployed to meet big problems” (Mazzucato, 2018). ‘Missions’ are at the core of new €100bn EU proposal for Horizon Europe (released June 2018). Some of the greatest technical achievements have resulted from missions (e.g. Apollo mission). Missions provide a solution, an opportunity, and an approach to address the numerous challenges that people face in their daily lives. Missions should consist of political agenda setting and civic engagement, clear & targeted missions, and a portfolio of projects that allow for bottom-up experimentation. 5 criteria for selecting missions: 1) Bold, inspirational, with wide societal relevance; 2) Clear direction: measurable, time-bound; 3) Ambitious but realistic R&I activities; 4) Cross-disciplinary, cross-sectoral, and cross-actor, and 5) Multiple, bottom-up solutions.
 - From a theoretical standpoint, traditional R&I policies have been accused of having low additionality and of capture by the status quo: they support activities would have been carried out anyway, generally by powerful, established incumbents (Frenken, 2017). A mission-driven R&I framework could help address both criticisms: by definition, missions involve combinations of knowledge residing in faraway parts of the innovation system. This should yield new ideas for which there is not a market yet (otherwise they would already be deployed to address the mission) (Autio, 2011). This could involve new players sitting in the intersection between disciplines, and with a greater tolerance for risk.
 - Designing and targeting these programmes requires a system for labelling disciplines and organisations based on their potential relevance for achieving a mission, and precise information about the structure of research networks (ie what disciplines are already collaborating with each other). Missions also seek to foster public debates and marshal support around more socially-oriented R&I policies but this information is difficult to monitor. We propose to focus this pilot on one of the missions proposed by Mariana Mazzucato in her February 2018 report on Mission-oriented innovation (e.g. on decreasing the burden of Dementia).

Figure: Example mission (Mazzucato 2018, p. 26)

- **Stakeholder engagement summary**

- **Defining missions:** When does a mission start and how broad it is? This pilot could define missions at the level of society, or of specific challenges or projects. Different questions are more relevant for different levels. For example, understanding how social needs are articulated into missions relates to the societal level; understanding what is the best language to define a challenge relates to the project level. The above also relates to the metrics we use to define impacts. Societal missions / challenges are often vague in the metrics that will be used to assess success so these might have to be determined as part of the pilot. Narrower missions tend to make their goals operational so they can be used to assess success.
- **Generality vs breadth:** Is there a one-size-fits-all infrastructure for data collection and analysis? Missions have very varied goals, from reducing youth debt to removing plastic from the oceans. Although there are some shared datasets that could be used to understand capabilities and activities around specific mission areas, completely different data sources to measure impacts might be relevant for different missions. In some cases the relevant data will only be available in proprietary / closed sources (eg banks in the case of youth debt) so accessing it will be difficult. Developing an extensive template to build mission evidence bases: One option would be to focus the pilot on a specific mission. Some of its components (eg.

data sources, analysis, visualisations) may be applicable to all missions while others would be mission specific.

- **Data sources - Social media biases:** Although social media could help measure societal needs and interest in a mission, it is important to be careful with these data, given their significant participation biases.
- **Applications - Predictive analyses:** There was strong interest on the development of tools or platforms that help predict the likelihood that a given project / team will be able to address a mission or challenge, and of the language for challenges which is more conducive to successful projects.

Relevance to RITO criteria

- **Relevant:** Highly relevant for new R&I policy frameworks in the EU.
- **Inclusive:** We will incorporate information about civil society interests, and the activities of informal networks and communities (eg in Meetup).
- **Trusted:** The pilot will combine established and new data sources. Findings will be validated with a panel of experts.
- **Open:** To the greatest extent possible, this pilot will aim to use data that are openly available.

Research/policy questions

- **Question:** What type (and intensity?) of research and innovation is required to address the mission in question? In particular, what type of interdisciplinarity?
 - For example, missions around climate change may require greater investment in understanding and addressing issues such as policy lock-in, free-ridership, and psychological barriers to behaviour change than in developing new technologies, just as the mission to the moon required innovations outside of space flight (e.g. in food and textiles).
- **Question:** What 'vocabulary' characterises a mission? Based on, for instance, the description of the dementia mission in the Mazzucato paper, we can query the data, identifying relevant bodies of knowledge related to dementia and their positions in the network. We can then create an overlay map of disciplines and technologies that are applied in similar areas to identify gaps and opportunities for collaboration.
- **Other topics to explore:** Large-scale analysis of technology readiness levels within scientific literature and the level of public awareness around the mission.

Data sources and methods

- **Data sources:** Publication and pre-print data, patents, research funding, social media and web data.
- **Data infrastructure and analytics:**
 - We will use Clio¹ to search for key terms / issues / challenges / relevant disciplines / actors for a mission (eg includes identifying other actors who have funded a mission). Having done this, we will produce maps of activity and networks / metrics for interdisciplinary collaboration, and social media data to measure public opinions around the mission.

¹ An innovation information retrieval system that Nesta started developing for the European Innovation Scoreboard. Clio uses keyword-based searches to identify relevant documents in a corpus.

- In order to move through different levels of granularity from grand challenges to missions to projects/initiatives, the pilot will involve layered network modelling and nested clustering to identify relevant clusters/communities/modules and their interfaces.

Outputs and preliminary findings

- The pilot will use state-of-the-art data science methods and innovative visualisations. We are particularly interested in promoting the use of metrics capturing relations or changes in the structure of collaboration networks that can help to deliver missions.
- This pilot's outputs will include an assessment of the knowledge base / networks for the case mission we focus on, and prototype visualisations to explore the data.

Limitations

- In order to ensure this pilot is feasible to carry out, the research team has decided to focus on one mission area. Some stakeholders expressed concern about the potential transferability/applicability of data sources, analysis, visualisations to multiple mission areas (which may be quite different from one another). To increase the chances that the data / analytics / visualisations for the pilot can be used in the analysis of other challenges, we will build a modular infrastructure that can be expanded to incorporate new data particularly relevant for other challenges, e.g. plastics in the ocean.

Validation and ongoing stakeholder engagement

- As the pilot progresses and continues to take shape, we will engage in a bilateral manner with people who have expressed interest in this pilot (e.g. through the Knowledge Stakeholder Workshop). We may also engage with a wider audience, including subject matter experts in the selection mission (e.g. dementia) who can provide content validation, as well as academics and others active in the ever-emerging discourse around the 'mission-oriented' agenda (e.g. Mission-Oriented Innovation Network at UCL).

Considerations for scaling up

- An absence of meaningful engagement with stakeholders could result in limited uptake.
- Most data sources we plan to incorporate have international coverage, in several cases going beyond the EU.
- Technical and practical feasibility should not be problematic as the pilot relies mostly on open data / data available through APIs.
- Clio, the information retrieval system that we have developed for the emerging technology pilot will also be relevant here.

Relevant conferences or events

- A poster presenting early stage findings could be submitted to the 17th International Conference on Scientometrics and Infometrics in Rome (submission deadline March 15 2019, conference September 2019)
- Early-stage findings could potentially be shared at a March 2019 event currently being planned by Nesta, the OECD and the European Commission.

- Domain-specific conferences and events will also be considered as venues for presenting this work.

References

DG RTD, Mazzucato (2018) Mission-Oriented R&I in the European Union

Foray, D., D. C. Mowery and R. R. Nelson (2012). "Public R&D and social challenges: What lessons from mission R&D programs?." *Research Policy* 41(10): 1697-1702. Available here.

Frenken, K. (2017). A Complexity-Theoretic Perspective on Innovation Policy. *Complexity, Governance & Networks, Complexity, Innovation and Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.20377/cgn-41>

Gustafsson, R., & Autio, E. (2011). A failure trichotomy in knowledge exploration and exploitation. *Research Policy*, 40(6), 819-831.

Virginia Polytechnic, Charles Goodsell (2011) Mission Mystique: Strength at the Institutional Centre

SPRU, Mazzucato and Universite Paris-Est (LISIS), Market Creation and the European Space Agency

Pilot 6: Advanced R&I funding analytics

Summary

This pilot would seek to develop more advanced metrics on European R&I funding data. Specifically, it would aim to explore if variables such as team collaboration, consortium skills diversity and project dissemination are good predictors for the outputs of European R&I projects. It would also seek to explore how projects evolve over time, including whether a convergence in language between disciplines can be detected from project conception to completion, and how such convergence relates to outputs.

Background/context

- Brief literature review

In a bid to demonstrate the added value of EU programmes, Horizon 2020 indicators emphasise assessing impact on European scientific and technological performance and research capacity, as well as any broader impact on the European economy and society. The Horizon 2020 indicators report (doi:10.2777/71098) contains a list of 23 compulsory key performance indicators (pages 11-15) and 14 cross-cutting issues (pages 16-19) which form the basis of the Horizon 2020 monitoring and evaluation framework. While these indicators form a robust basis for an M&E framework they mostly consist of traditional indicators such as aggregates (e.g. total number of SME's introducing market innovations) each evaluated independently of one another with no multivariate considerations or analysis of geographies, network properties of the interactions between actors, or language. This pilot proposes to develop more advanced metrics on European R&I funding by augmenting existing approaches with new variables such as skills diversity; generating new indicators that seek to capture intangible outputs using big data and machine learning techniques; and combining this indicator portfolio within an interpretable multivariate framework in which indicators are considered in unison and not isolation in order to understand the nuances and trade-offs present.

Stakeholder engagement summary

A wide array of gaps in current funding analytics and important considerations have been identified through stakeholder engagement workshops.

The biggest group consensus was centred around the fact that current funding analytics tend to attempt to boil things down to a one-size-fits-all number which may make a metric clearer for a decision maker to understand but at the cost of removing nuance. More advanced funding analytics need to be easily communicable whilst being general enough to account for heterogeneity in subject areas; institutional goals; project goals etc. For example, different disciplines have different citation distributions and behaviours which are not reflected by comparing citation counts/indices across disciplines or looking at impact factors.

A fruitful discussion on potential missing indicators of success was also had with team diversity being flagged as somethings that was typically completely overlooked in current assessments. Furthermore, it was suggested that the market environment around the technology being developed over the course of a project can play a key role in the success of a project - if the technology is not ready to be absorbed by the market then a projects impact may be stunted. Finally, it was remarked that institutions that possess a wealth of experience in a domain or are well connected within the

collaborative network are also likely to be big predictors of success. The final pair of discussion points centred around expanding the definition of success. Firstly, the impact of funding a project is not constrained to the outputs of that particular project but will have trickle-down effects to the subsequent projects participants are involved in. This is an understudied aspect perhaps due to the fact that it is not directly measurable through a simplistic metric such as number of papers or number of citations a project has generated. The second strand of this theme closely relates to the first - a project may have cross-sectional impact where a project seeds a massive explosion of growth in a distantly related field (which may not be attributed back to the project beyond the first few citations as subsequent works will be more relevant to the new domain.

Relevance to RITO criteria

- RITO assessment:
 - Relevant: This pilot could contribute to the improved monitoring and evaluation of R&I projects, and is therefore likely to be highly relevant to policymakers.
 - Inclusive: Building on previous research in the area of multidisciplinary, we seek to further develop metrics around the extent to which diverse viewpoints can contribute to successful outputs such as papers and patents.
 - Trusted: Given that the CORDIS dataset has been created by the Commission, it is highly trusted.
 - Open: The data is available with permission.

Research/policy questions

- Using features of the CORDIS dataset we propose to build a machine learning model to predict project outputs in SESAM (the European Commission's online reporting tool for Research and Technological projects) such as research excellence (e.g. highly cited papers) and patents. The model will be constructed in an interpretable manner in order to maximise understanding across the funding portfolio rather than being a tool to make individual funding decisions. As discussed during the stakeholder engagement workshops there are many heterogeneities such as competing priorities within the funding landscape, therefore the developed model will exploit hierarchical methods to account for this.
- A further policy question relates to whether the research that was funded was performed, and if the proposal and outputs differ then is this for better or for worse? By collecting the text for project proposals and of project outputs, we will use Natural Language Processing techniques such as topic modelling to assess the similarity of proposals and outcomes whilst controlling for different language likely to be used in the two contexts.
- Many R&I awards consist of many who may not share a common language with which to talk about the project, either due to concepts being unknown to one party or both parties having different terminology for the same concept. This difference may be present across many different levels - between nations, between scientific disciplines or between academia and industry. It is therefore natural to assume that projects that fail to overcome these differences are less likely to collaborate and generate

innovations. With this in mind we propose to identify projects that consist of a diverse range of participants and assess the similarity of grantee language both before and after the funding period in order to assess whether a convergence in language occurs and whether the extent of this convergence predicts the success of the project. The investigation of this question could be performed across all relevant awards or a small number of awards could be picked for more in depth case studies.

Data sources and methods

- Methods:
 - Use of unsupervised machine learning to identify clusters within H2020 projects and institutions.
 - Use of supervised learning to predict outcomes of H2020 projects.
 - Name disambiguation to identify individuals on Twitter or Microsoft Academic Graph.
 - Data enrichment with spatial information.
 - Data collection using APIs (Twitter, Microsoft Academic Knowledge) and potentially web scraping (company websites to find their domain of activities)
 - Natural Language Processing
- Data, metadata and process infrastructure:
 - CORDIS
 - SESAM/OpenAire
 - Twitter
 - Academic publications (MAK)
 - Company websites (using URLs from CORDIS)
 - Crossref
- Relevant tools/infrastructure
 - Web mining tool that has been applied to scraping company websites:
<https://github.com/datawizard1337/ARGUS>

Outputs and preliminary findings

The ideal approach to visualisation will be decided following further refinement of the research questions, methodologies and findings.

The following list provides a sense of the various ways in which CORDIS data have been visualised to date:

- <http://h2020viz.vinnova.se/#/>
- <https://openknowledgemaps.org/viper/index.php>
- <https://cordis.europa.eu/datalab/>
- <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/dashboard/hub/>

Limitations

- The primary limitation is likely to be our ability to link and disambiguate between multiple data sources - e.g. identifying which “John Smith” is a chemist and which “John Smith” is a biologist and which of the two owns the twitter handle “@JSmith”. It is impossible to do this perfectly therefore care needs to be taken to minimise noise introduced at this stage of the pipeline.

Part of this is mitigated by utilising existing, sophisticated solutions such as Microsoft Academic Knowledge, Crossref, OpenAire developer API which implement parts of this process, whilst augmenting these with additional layers of verification and analysis.

- Lack of counterfactual/control data - in an ideal world we would have data from a cohort of unfunded projects to evaluate future outcomes/outputs of the unsuccessful institutions and researchers.

We currently have no way acquiring this data (if indeed it exists), therefore we need to be careful about the inferences we draw with one possibility being to compare to the average researcher/institution within a certain context (e.g. discipline/geography).

Validation and ongoing stakeholder engagement

- Preliminary results will be shared and validated with contacts within DG RTD. A broader set of stakeholders, particularly attendees from the two EURITO workshops conducted to date, will also be consulted.

Considerations for scaling up

- Given that the data sources cover most if not all European countries and is application domain agnostic, scaling of this pilot is unlikely to be problematic.
- The team undertaking the work should have the necessary capacity to perform any scale-up work in-house.

Relevant conferences or events

- A poster presenting early stage findings could be submitted to the 17th International Conference on Scientometrics and Infometrics in Rome (submission deadline March 15 2019, conference September 2019)
- Early-stage findings could potentially be shared at a March 2019 event currently being planned by Nesta, the OECD and the European Commission.

References

Campbell, P. (2008). Escape from the impact factor. *Ethics in science and environmental politics*, 8(1), 5-7.

Curtis, B. (2008). The performance-based research fund: Research assessment and funding in New Zealand. *Globalisation, societies and education*, 6(2), 179-194.

Horizon 2020 indicators. Assessing the results and impact of Horizon" 24 Sep. 2015, <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/news/horizon-2020-indicators-assessing-results-and-impact-horizon>.

Lane, J. (2010). Let's make science metrics more scientific. *Nature*, 464(7288), 488

Leiden Manifesto. Retrieved October 31, 2018, from <http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>

McKeown, K., Daume III, H., Chaturvedi, S., Paparrizos, J., Thadani, K., Barrio, P., ... & Gravano, L. (2016). Predicting the impact of scientific concepts using full-text features. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67(11), 2684-2696.

Nelson, A., Earle, A., Howard-Grenville, J., Haack, J., & Young, D. (2014). Do innovation measures actually measure innovation? Obliteration, symbolic adoption, and other finicky challenges in tracking innovation diffusion. *Research Policy*, 43(6), 927-940.

Kaur, J., Radicchi, F., & Menczer, F. (2013). Universality of scholarly impact metrics. *Journal of Informetrics*, 7(4), 924-932.

Pilot 7: Inclusive Innovation

Summary

The overall aim of this pilot will be to develop **new indicators on inclusive R&I** that will provide policymakers with a more nuanced view of the key social, industrial and/or geographic disparities in the R&I landscape.

Background/context

- **Inclusive innovation:** Inequality of both opportunities and outcomes have become a central focus of governments throughout the world as evidence on the negative social, political and economic consequences of these disparities continues to mount. Due to its central role underpinning skills and productivity, the R&I system, including its policies, actors and outputs, has become a central locus for an increasingly heated debate about who loses and benefits from the profound innovation-induced socio-technological changes currently underway. Critics of the status quo argue that a lack of inclusiveness in the R&I system have contributed to a wide range of non-inclusive services and products that largely reflect and entrench systemic biases of those holding positions of power in within the existing institutional framework. The insular and exclusive nature of R&I systems has also been associated with more troubling trends within society such as a backlash against expertise and embrace of populist ideologies across notable pockets of Western society.
- Examinations of the R&I system's level of inclusiveness tend to cut across three interrelated key facets:
 - **Social:** Certain groups (e.g. women, ethnic minorities, people with disabilities) have been consistently underrepresented within the R&I landscape, owing in part to an interplay between lower capacities (i.e. skills for innovation, including tech skills, managerial skills) due to lower levels of training as well as, in many contexts, broader systemic and cultural barriers to educational and labour force participation and progression.
 - **Industrial (firms/sectors):** An uneven distribution of innovation capacity across sectors and firms has widened the productivity gap, leading to a “dual economy problem” whereby innovative and technologically advanced, highly productive sectors coexist alongside traditional, low-productivity sectors that derive little benefit from new technology.
 - **Territorial:** The existing R&I system has been extensively critiqued for creating and/or exacerbating geographical inequalities, with highly productive companies tending to cluster (often by design) within a select number of neighbourhoods, cities or regions.
- **The role of innovation policy:** Traditional innovation policies may contribute to inequalities through the provision of opportunities to those with specific skill sets (e.g. excellence grants, scholarships); offering incentives that in practice only a small number of firms can benefit from (e.g. R&D tax credits tend to be taken up primarily by large companies); public procurement policies benefiting incumbent firms and discouraging newcomers; investing resources in regions where public laboratories are located. Issues of inclusiveness within the research system have arguably received greater attention than within innovation, however ample opportunities exist to improve and broaden and/or deepen the scope of these assessments using new data and

analytics. Innovation policies may also foster inclusiveness, for example through the development of affordable and appropriate goods and services that meet the needs of lower-income or other excluded/disadvantaged groups.

- **Inclusive growth:** Innovation policy plays a central role in promoting growth, and increasingly, inclusive innovation has become a focal point in trying to understand the drivers of inclusive growth. However, the concept of inclusive growth has been critiqued for being a fuzzy concept that is vaguely and inconsistently defined, and therefore risks losing meaning and complicating measurement of both its implementation and impacts. The term followed ‘pro-poor growth’, which gained popularity from late 1990s to mid-2000s but implementation was hard to track because different actors defined it inconsistently. Inclusive growth risks repeating these mistakes. There is little evidence of what works, particularly at the level of cities — where the inclusive growth agenda has been most vigorously adopted — which may have limited power and resources relative to national governments. Some notable attempts at measuring inclusive growth include the Metro Monitor of the Brookings Institution, which defines inclusive growth as: 1. The overall size of economy (measured through jobs, new firms, output); 2. A measure of prosperity (productivity, average wages or standard of living); and 3. Some indicator of narrowing economic disparity (either ‘general’ with employment, middle-class wages, working poverty or ‘racial’ - outcomes for whites and people of colour).

- **Stakeholder engagement summary (EURITO)**
 - **Societal engagement with R&I:** Including society in R&I is an important but perhaps underappreciated dimension of inclusiveness. Citizen science - indicators could be developed around means of engagement, intensity of engagement, topics, participants, citizens included in patents, papers. [note: some very basic indicators exist, developed for the Open Science Monitor Project]
 - **Inclusiveness of R&I policies:** For example, the data on gender equality plans within universities is currently collected via survey but the data have much room for improvement. A web scraping approach could theoretically be an option for trying to collect this. The OECD’s STIP database contains policies from multiple countries. It could be interesting to use a combination of NLP and/or crowd coding to explore how inclusiveness and equity issues are being discussed.
 - **Positions of leadership:** For example, Grade A in the higher education sector is a key indicator for tracking gender equality in the HES - a ‘grade A’ equivalent for business enterprise sector would be interesting.
 - **Trajectories and mobility:** It would be possible to explore the ‘trajectories’ of people within the RI system using data sources such as Orcid and Crunchbase. Movement of women/men researchers currently captured in MORE2 survey, but there is room for improvement. Unclear whether indicators exist on the movement of entrepreneurs, and whether these have an inclusivity dimension
 - **Contextual influences on inclusiveness:** Awareness and other metrics of quality of life (e.g. social policies, childcare options) would be important for interpreting findings. Combining multiple dimensions of the above and performing geographical analyses would provide a deeper insight into location-based challenges and opportunities for inclusive RI.

Relevance to RITO criteria

- **Relevant:** As described above, the topic of inclusiveness in R&I is increasingly pressing to address. There are ample opportunities to expand the scope and depth of the data in this area.
- **Inclusive:** Inclusivity is at the core of the proposed pilot.
- **Trusted and timely:** Trust will be established through an in-depth assessment of which data to include, and in-depth auditing of the data sources to ensure that any biases or shortcomings can be clearly articulated. Additionally, relevant consultations on the ethics of exploring topics such as gender and ethnicity will be carried out. Selection of data sources will privilege those that are more up-to-date.
- **Open:** To the greatest extent possible, this pilot will aim to use data that are openly available.

Research/policy questions

The first two questions to be addressed in this pilot aim to establish the fundamental groundwork for the development of inclusive innovation indicators by clarifying its logic and mechanisms, as well as an exploration of the ways in which aspects of inclusiveness are currently being addressed in policy documents.

- **Question 1:** What is the causal logic behind inclusive innovation? To what extent, and through what mechanisms, does it influence inclusive growth? Where is the evidence base strong and where are there weaknesses?
- **Question 2:** To what extent is inclusivity (along social, industrial, and territorial or other lines) addressed within research and innovation policies? When did different dimensions of inclusiveness emerge?

The third set of questions to be explored will be heavily influenced by the findings from the first and second streams of questions. Indicatively, however, some questions are provided below.

- **Question 3:** For example, what is the diversity profile of companies in different emerging sectors? (e.g. what proportion of UK firms specialising in immersive technologies are headed by women and/or ethnic minorities?) What contextual or company characteristics predict higher diversity? To what extent are diverse emerging firms and sectors geospatially clustered?

Data sources and methods

- **Data sources:** A wide variety of traditional and novel data sources are being assessed for inclusion, including:
 - **Firms/sectors:** Crunchbase, business web data, Companies House
 - **Digital innovation:** GitHub
 - **Informal networking:** Meetup
 - **Research and innovation policies:** OECD Scientific and Technological Policy corpus of substantive reports (782 full documents from 1994-2016), Research Policy articles (2527 title-abstracts over 1988-2017), Research and Innovation Observatory Horizon 2020 Policy Support Facility, JRC RIO Library (1650 R&I policy documents)
- **Data infrastructure and methods:** The specific type of data infrastructure and analytics required will be determined once data sources are selected. Analytics are

likely to include supervised machine learning and natural language processing. Indicatively, however, work will be conducted primarily in Python using Jupyter notebooks, which will then be shared on GitHub.

Outputs and preliminary findings

- The output of this pilot would be a collection of inclusive innovation indicators, accompanied by engaging visualisations highlighting geographic and other key disparities. Additional outputs from the 'groundwork' aspect of the pilot could include expert-validated causal model(s) on inclusive innovation and inclusive growth, as well as their relationship to one another.

Risks and limitations

- Concept of inclusive innovation is deeply entangled with other types of innovation that deal with bottom-up approaches, social equity concerns or diversity in decisions/products/outcomes, including: bottom of the pyramid, frugal, grassroots, social, responsible, democratisation, open. Multiple institutional/situational/locational loci (research, entrepreneurship, SMEs, corporations, sectoral), geographic (developed vs. developing, rural vs. urban). This is one of the drivers for the first pilot question to develop a causal model, which should ultimately clarify how this concept is constructed. Given the challenges around identifying and evidencing causal links, however, any outcomes derived from this will need to be cautiously interpreted.
- Given the wide range of topics that could potentially fall under the umbrella of inclusive innovation, there is a risk that the pilot identified will not capture the most relevant/important dimension for decision-makers. This will be mitigated by a robust consultative and literature review phase early in the Exploration Phase.
- Relative to other pilots, a pilot focusing on inclusivity may have a greater focus on individuals. It will be necessary to observe best practices in the ethics of working with individual-level data wherever appropriate.
- While almost all indicators risk being 'gamed' by actors who wish to improve their standing, any indicators based on the analysis of textual descriptions of R&I policies pose an even higher risk (actors may simply change the language of their policies to make them sound more inclusive).

Validation and ongoing stakeholder engagement

- **Steps to validate the pilot:**
 - **Exploration phase:** Ongoing, bilateral stakeholder engagement will be carried out throughout the Exploration Phase to ensure timely feedback is obtained on the pilot. In early 2019, we will endeavour to hold a small workshop with some key stakeholders in order to validate early findings emerging from the pilots.
 - **Post-exploration phase:** As per the agreement at the September 2018 Project Assembly Meeting, this pilot will be validated within the broader portfolio of Wave 2 pilots.
- **Ongoing and potential stakeholder engagement (names omitted):**
 - Inclusive Innovation team at Nesta and their network of contacts
 - OECD authored report on inclusive innovation policies, maintains database of science, technology and innovation policies
 - DG RTD's Science with and for Society (unit B7) is interested in championing pilots on gender equality in R&I

- Professor at LSE - expert on inclusive growth and innovation
- International Science and Innovation Directorate, BEIS. Currently working on a new project on inclusive growth.
- Members of the UK Innovation Caucus - an initiative funded by Innovate UK and the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC). Currently developing a line of work on black, asian and minority ethnic groups in UK innovation.
- Inclusive Models team, Scottish Enterprise
- UNESCO Inclusive Policy Lab
- West Midlands Inclusive Growth

Considerations for scaling up

- Given the high level of interest in inclusive innovation amongst policy-makers and the relative dearth of evidence to inform/support/evaluate these policies, this pilot could potentially be very promising in terms of uptake.
- Feasibility of scaling pilot up to a European level depends largely on the data sources selected, however certain components should already be feasible to analyse at European level. Other data sources (e.g. full-text policy documents) may be more difficult to analyse at scale, particularly if the methods used rely on the development of a set of relevant keywords, as these may not translate accurately or fully capture relevant phenomena in all languages.
- No specialised tools or skills are anticipated to be required, and therefore this pilot does not require any special procurement considerations.
- The data collected for other EURITO pilots (e.g. Pilot 1 on emerging technology ecosystems) could be used as inputs to explore different dimensions of inclusivity.

Relevant conferences or events

- The pilot has already been discussed at numerous roundtable/bilateral meetings on inclusive innovation, including:
 - A UK Innovation Caucus roundtable regarding Innovate UK's plans to develop programmes around the engagement of black, asian and minority ethnic groups (London, 1 October 2018)
 - A Nesta-led roundtable that brought together a small group of leading academics and practitioners to discuss definitions, challenges and opportunities in the space of inclusive innovation (London, 23 October 2018).
- Multiple additional meetings (e.g. Centre for Cities, Government of Scotland, Scottish Enterprise, and with an academic from LSE,) have shown that there is a great deal of interest in exploring the measurement of inclusive innovation. We therefore anticipate that there will be a plentitude of opportunities in which to present our work over the remainder of the EURITO project period.
- Early-stage findings could potentially be shared at a March 2019 event currently being planned by Nesta, the OECD and the European Commission.

References

Chataway, J., Hanlin, R., & Kaplinsky, R. (2014). Inclusive innovation: an architecture for policy development. *Innovation and Development*, 4(1), 33-54.

Edler, J., & Fagerberg, J. (2017). Innovation policy: What, why, and how. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 33(1), 2-23.

Heeks, R., Amalia, M., Kintu, R., & Shah, N. (2013). Inclusive innovation: definition, conceptualisation and future research priorities. IDPM Development Informatics Working Papers.

Lee, N. (2018). Inclusive Growth in cities: a sympathetic critique. *Regional Studies*, 1-11.

Owen, R., Macnaghten, P., & Stilgoe, J. (2012). Responsible research and innovation: From science in society to science for society, with society. *Science and public policy*, 39(6), 751-760.

Planes-Satorra, S., & Paunov, C. (2017). Inclusive innovation policies.

Schot, J., & Steinmueller, W. E. (2018). Three frames for innovation policy: R&D, systems of innovation and transformative change. *Research Policy*, 47(9), 1554-1567.

Zehavi, A., & Breznitz, D. (2017). Distribution sensitive innovation policies: Conceptualization and empirical examples. *Research Policy*, 46(1), 327-336.

Pilot 8: Linkages and knowledge exchange indicators (healthtech)

Summary

- The focus of this pilot is on mapping R&I-related knowledge exchange and information flow, including the analysis of R&I linkages and their impact. We use the Danish health-tech R&I ecosystem as the application domain in order to increase the feasibility of data gathering and allow for a more in-depth interpretation of results with domain experts. For this purpose we have had discussions with the NovoNordisk Foundation and The Copenhagen Center for Health Technology [Cachet], who act as part of our stakeholders in this pilot.

Background/context

- Opportunity: With the increasing interest in an ecosystem view of R&I phenomena we are facing a need for new indicators able to capture R&I-related knowledge exchange, including the analysis of R&I linkages and their impact. Unless we understand the relations of information flow, collaborations and other interactions within R&I ecosystems we risk missing opportunities to improve the allocation of resources, the design of regulations and the evaluation of R&I progress.
- Application domain: The overall application domain can be described as the “Health-tech ecosystem”. In this context, health-tech can be broadly understood as “technology to improve the design and delivery of healthcare”. This form of technology is considered one of the key elements needed to reduce the cost and quality of healthcare systems worldwide. Despite the potential of many new generation health technologies we face a number of challenges including costs, adoption, usability, trust, system integration, etc. We are proposing this application domain because:
 - Its inherent potential for societal impact (market-pull).
 - Worldwide availability of data sources, both traditional and non-traditional.
 - We have access to application domain experts who can help us to validate and interpret our results.
- Flexibility of application domain: We aim to design the indicators to measure linkages and information exchange in such a way that they can be transferred across domains with minimal need for modifications. Since the current method that we are applying requires the input of bibliometric/scientometric-type of data (or data of similar nature) as long as this type of data exists in the application domain of interest, it will be possible to extend the analysis to additional domains.
- Assessment of 'periphery to core of R&I policy' capacity of proposed pilot: There are no mature/commonly adopted indicators for R&I-related knowledge exchange/flow, including the analysis of R&I linkages and its impact. Taking such “peripheric” indicators into the core can be facilitated by the champions that we have considered for this pilot, namely the NovoNordisk Foundation that brings its vast experience measuring impact and CACHET who are healthtech specialists and have strong ties with both the private and public sector in Denmark.
- Stakeholder engagement summary
 - We have engaged in this challenge primarily with NovoNordisk Foundation, which has provided us with internal data and feedback to validate our findings.

- The feedback received so far has been positive. One of the main distinctive advantages that has been highlighted is that this type of linkage-based indicators are able to focus on the ecosystem of solution providers and technologies, rather than individual funds or groups. As a result, linkage indicators are seen as an important complements to traditional indicators that otherwise underestimate the impact of chains of links.
- Feedback highlights from the knowledge stakeholder workshop (KSW) include
 - a) research impact can also be measured analysing the number of representatives of particular research communities in documents. For example, number of people affiliated to editorial boards of journals, ministries, committees, etc.
 - b) we could try to connect new data sources that contain contextual information about impact such as traditional output-focused indicators for R&D (e.g. patent number) or compare the results against cases that are considered to have had a high impact (for example via # mentions or qualitative case descriptions), and
 - c) it is important to consider that knowledge does not flow through only one channel – it may spread across multiple routes. As a result it is not immediately obvious the best technique that should be used to quantify the strength of multiple ties.

Relevance to RITO criteria

- **Relevant:** The pilot tackles an issue that has already been mentioned as necessary to improve in the context of R&D indicators, and it is also of high societal relevance.
- **Inclusive:** We are starting with a scoping exercise focused in Denmark. However data-modelling and all the methods applied can be transferred worldwide. Our emphasis is also in network structure, not scale - we believe this helps to highlight issues of team diversity and flows of information across disciplinary, organisational, geographical and topical boundaries. Furthermore, we combine industrial and academic outputs and the data inputs can be expanded to include SMEs and any other data-source available.
- **Timely:** Our inclusion of data sources other than patents and publications allow us to identify signals that might be expressed earlier on in other sources. For example we are evaluating data from national business registries and repositories of health-tech organisations and projects created by organisations like <http://www.cachet.dk/> as a starting point to start mapping additional data sources.
- **Trusted:** Combining traditional/curated data sources with non-traditional sources allows us to leverage the trust put in official sources whilst also enjoying the complementary advantages of alternative sources.
- **Open:** All our core proposed methods and data for this proposed pilot are already publicly available. The closed data provided by NovoNordisk Foundation is currently only used for validation and to co-create a model that can be interpreted by our target stakeholders. We will also document the analytical steps taken so that they are reproducible.

Research/policy questions

- What is the volume and impact of information flow, collaborations and other relations that occur in a given R&I ecosystem?
- What metrics best describe key structural characteristics in an R&I ecosystem?

Data sources and methods

Source	Status	Observations
Scientific publications data	We are incorporating publication data from Web of Science and a sample of publications provided by NovoNordisk to triangulate and evaluate the impact of funding and linkages.	Web of Science requires a subscription (that most universities have) and allows data mining for research purposes. However for other uses or situations where a license is not available we can substitute Web of Science with open access publication repositories.
Research funding	We have analysed H2020 funding data	Exploring options to include data from other EU funding organisations
Internal data from NovoNordisk foundation for triangulation and validation of the identified linkages	We have included data provided by NovoNordisk foundation and we are using it to model the notion of linkages and validate our preliminary results	To scale up this model we will not rely on closed data, however the “closed” data that we are already using provides important validation and also dependent variables to test hypotheses.
Patents	We are planning to include in the analysis patents extracted from Derwent or equivalent patent data sources.	Derwent requires a subscription (which some universities have) and allows data mining for research purposes. However for other uses or situations where a license is not available we can substitute Derwent with open patent publication databases (e.g. patent lens).

The first step requires the normalisation of the data through an ETL process that allows us to load semi-structured data into a graph database. Within the graph database we apply network analysis techniques to map flows and relations and to quantify structural features of the network.

- Identification of main entities within overall dataset using entity extraction approaches
- Development of graph models able to capture the network structure of the network of collaborations and interactions
- Design and implementation of algorithms to measure information flow and exchange.
- Development and testing of visualisations to communicate information flow and exchange in an easily “digestible” format

Outputs and preliminary findings

- We are experimenting with a range of network and matrix based approaches to visualise network structures, flows and relations. In addition to these approaches we also aim at transferring the results into more conventional representations showing relations and paths at different levels of analysis.

Limitations

- The main limitation of the method applied on this pilot relate to the discretionary decisions needed to define what a chain of linkages is and the weight of each linkage. At the moment we are focusing on links related to evolving co-authorships, co-funding relations, and thematic connections without defining different weights for each of them. However, this might change depending of the feedback we receive during validation.

Validation and ongoing stakeholder engagement

- We have actively engaged with NovoNordisk foundation (NNFs), in particular their impact assessment team, whom have been studying multiple methods to assess the impact of NNF investments in the healthcare technology area and as a result can provide direct means for validation of our findings.
- The second step is to engage more actively with Cachet (Copenhagen Centre for Healthcare Technologies) to obtain a more systemic understanding and validation of our findings in the context of health-technology linkages within Denmark.

Considerations for scaling up

Complementarities with other pilots

- The most promising complementarity is with “Pilot 6: Advanced R&I funding analytics” where indicators of linkages in the context of funding analysis can prove to be a useful addition to understand how the structural characteristics of a chain composed by multiple linkages describe (or not) quantitative and qualitative features of a particular grant.

Scaling up

- Although for resource and time constraint reasons we are starting with Denmark, we don’t see any fundamental constraint to achieve European-level coverage if more resources and time are invested.

Tools

- The main tools used in this pilot are a Graph Database running on Neo4j, Python and Jupyter Notebooks (where we have documented each step of the process).

Relevant conferences or events

- Danish High Tech Summit - Healthcare Track (<https://www.hightechsummit.dk/>)

- Participation and prize in Skylab Open Innovation X HEALTH (Oi-X Health 2018 <http://www.cachet.dk/news/2018/04/open-innovation-x-health-case-competition?id=c03a8055-d9bd-4468-8eae-112e5623878e>)

References

Ahuja, G. (2000). The duality of collaboration: Inducements and opportunities in the formation of interfirm linkages. *Strategic management journal*, 21(3), 317-343.

Durugbo, C., Hutabarat, W., Tiwari, A., & Alcock, J. R. (2011). Modelling collaboration using complex networks. *Information Sciences*, 181(15), 3143-3161.

Fonseca, B. P., Fernandes, E., & Fonseca, M. V. (2017). Collaboration in science and technology organizations of the public sector: A network perspective. *Science and Public Policy*, 44(1), 37-49.

Myers, C. R. (2003). Software systems as complex networks: Structure, function, and evolvability of software collaboration graphs. *Physical Review E*, 68(4), 046116.

Sonnenwald, D. H. (2007). Scientific collaboration. *Annual review of information science and technology*, 41(1), 643-681.

Prota, L., Vitale, M. P., & D'Esposito, M. R. (2017). Topology and evolution of collaboration networks: the case of a policy-anchored district. In *Knowledge and Networks* (pp. 169-190). Springer, Cham.

Parraguez, P., Eppinger, S. D., & Maier, A. M. (2015). Information flow through stages of complex engineering design projects: a dynamic network analysis approach. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 62(4), 604-617.